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Mathematics from Daily Life

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Abstract

Mathematics is considered a very difficult, dull and boring subject. No doubt, Mathematics laboratory helps the teachers to make the mathematical concepts concrete and more understandable to the students. Being Mathematics teachers our duties do not stop just at the establishment of Mathematics laboratories and performing a few experiments mentioned in laboratory-manuals but we have to create the interest, the appreciation and the love for Mathematics among students. We have to arouse the will to learn Mathematics in students by relating it to their daily life, their daily needs. This article will help Mathematics teacher to understand the techniques and methods to create and relate concepts of Mathematics from daily life situations

Key Words: Mathematics from Daily Life, Mathematics, Mathematics and Daily Life Situations, Mathematics Teaching, Relating Mathematics to Life.

Introduction-

“Mathematics - a very difficult, dull and boring subject. I cannot study it with ease” – this dilemma is in the minds of almost all the students, they prey and hope for a miracle to happen that can escape them from studying Mathematics. What is the reason behind such fear? Who is responsible for this?

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Perhaps the answer lies in our traditional method of teaching – just a formal introduction of the formula/concept, citing two or more examples and assigning exercises to be solved from books as home-work in a dull and boring manner. And we expect that the students would learn the concepts thoroughly. But the students learn enough to get passed in the examination as it is mandatory for promotion to next class.

What is now? When there are reforms in education system those support for promotion of the student to the next class in spite of her achievements in the previous class. Now it is no more a necessity to pass the examination.

Are we aimless now? Was this the only aim of teaching Mathematics to the students? Will they be able to live happily and perform their duties even as a common person in our social set-up where Mathematics is required at each and every step?

We all are aware of this importance of Mathematics and wants to improve the situation. Therefore to improve the situation and to achieve the actual aims of teaching Mathematics, we have to create the interest of students in Mathematics. For this purpose, we have elaborated the concepts of “Mathematics Laboratory”.

No doubt, it is a very appreciable step, but will it alone be able to improve the situation? From past records, it is obvious that only a few students opt for pure sciences although they have the crutches of laboratories from decades. Establishment of laboratories and a few experiments in laboratories alone will not be capable to catch the interest of students.

It is true; Mathematics Laboratory will help the teachers to make the mathematical concepts concrete and more understandable to the students. Being Mathematics teachers our duties do not stop here just at the establishment of Mathematics

laboratories and performing a few experiments mentioned in laboratory-manuals but we have to create the interest, the appreciation and the love for Mathematics. We have to arouse the will to learn Mathematics in students by relating it to their daily life, their daily needs.

It sounds a little challenging. However, it is possible with little more efforts on the part of us, the teachers. Firstly, we have to find the interests of a common man. 'Interest' in a common person's view states, "my interest lies only in that what is useful to me either as a tool to perform my daily routines, earn bread or as a tool to relax and entertainment to revive my mind".

We have to start from this very view point of a common man to create interest of students in Mathematics. We have to make students realize the need and importance of learning Mathematics. We have to prepare a platform standing on which they can decide whether they want to learn mathematics or not.

And for this we not only have to correlate Mathematics to daily life but we have to regenerate and represent Mathematics from daily life. Our aim should not be only to 'to teach' Mathematics but 'to reorganize' learning of mathematics. Now the question arises how can we achieve this aim? Let us have some examples for achieving this aim:-

1. To Organize Learning of Concepts of Arithmetic-

A. **Aim:** To enable students to practice four fundamental rules of mathematics.

Level of Class: Elementary

Material Required: Packets of Biscuits, Toffees, Birthday Caps, Chocolates etc. according to the number of students and questions.

Procedure:

- (i) Ask students some very simple questions and give prize toffees / a packet of biscuits / chocolates / birthday caps for each correct answer.
- (ii) Announce that a complementary gift will be awarded to the student with maximum number of biscuits / chocolates / birthday caps.
- (iii) Ask the students to tell who has got the maximum number of toffees / a packet of biscuits / chocolates / birthday caps.
- (iv) Now compare the total number of prize items of a student with the others.

B. **Aim:** To enable students to understand the concept of fraction.

Level of Class: Elementary

Material Required: An Apple and A Knife.

Procedure:

- (i) Cut an apple into four equal parts.
- (ii) Ask some very simple questions and award the students with the pieces of the apple as:

1st prize winner = 2 pieces of apple
2nd prize winner = 1 piece of apple
- (iii) Now ask the students to count the total number of pieces.
- (iv) Again ask the students – how much part of the apple has been awarded to the 1st and 2nd prize winner and how much is left behind?

C. **Aim:** To enable students to learn the units of measurement

Level of Class: Elementary

Material Required: Measuring Instruments: Ruler, Measuring Tape, Weighting Scales etc.

Procedure:

- (i) Measure weight and height of each student and measure different articles with the help of students by using the different measuring instruments.
- (ii) Compare the units of measures of different parameters.
- (iii) To Organize Learning of Concepts of Arithmetic:

D. ***Aim:*** To enable students to understand the concept of profit and loss.

Level of Class: Elementary

Material Required: Dummy Currency Notes, Packet of Biscuits and Toffees bearing M.R.P., Balance Sheets.

Procedure:

- (i) Make three teams of the students.
 - A team – 2 Students
 - B and C team – 5 Students
- (ii) Give team A packets of biscuits and toffees only and instruct them to sell these to teams B and C on M.R.P. only.
- (iii) Give teams B and C equal packets of biscuits and toffees and dummy currency. Instruct them to sale and purchase goods from each other on a settled price by bargaining. They can also purchase goods from team A on M.R.P. only.
- (iv) Each team should be given items of equal worth. Announce that the winner will be the team that would have items of highest worth.
- (v) Ask each team to have written record of their money and goods, their record of sale and purchase on balance sheets.

- (vi) Now ask them to perform the activity that could last for ten minutes or above.
- (vii) Then ask each team to calculate their gains or losses and announce the winner.
- (viii) The above examples show us the path to make the students realize the need and importance of mathematics in their lives and motivate the students to learn Mathematics by creating their interest in Mathematics.

2. To Organize Learning of Concepts of Coordinate Geometry-

Aim: To enable students to plot the points and find the coordinate of points

Level of Class: Elementary

Material Required: Floor, Chalks, Pens, Papers etc.

Procedure:

- (i) Make two teams of students, six students in each team.
- (ii) Mark the Coordinate-axes on the floor by taking 1 unit = 1 foot.
- (iii) Call the first team and ask any five students of the team to stand on the Cartesian-plane in a straight line.
- (iv) Call the other team and ask any five students of the team to stand on the Cartesian-plane in a straight line.
- (v) Ask the sixth student of each team to mark the positions (Points) of his teammates.
- (vi) Now ask the students to find the co-ordinates of the marked points and the equation of the line.
- (vii) Announce the winner who completes the task at first.

3. To Organize Learning of Concepts of Geometry-

Aim: To enable students to recognize, classify and identify geometrical shapes and figures.

Level of Class: Elementary

Material Required: Small Sized Bindi (Point), Straws (Line), Windows of the Class-room, Chairs, Tables, Papers and Chalk Board (Quadrilateral, Plane), Clock (Angles), Mad Angles (Triangle), Football, Cricket Ball (Sphere), Bangles, Rings (Circle), Mehndi-cones (Cone), Tubes (Sphere) etc.

Procedure:

- (i) Arrange all the material in the class.
- (ii) Ask the students to collect the same type of goods.
- (iii) Now compare the collections with the help of students. e.g. compare shape of bangles with the shape of balls.
- (iv) Then list the properties of items in different collections with the help of students.

4. To Organize Learning of Concept of Probability-

Aim: To enable students to practice simple problems based on probability.

Level of Class: Secondary

Material Required: Two Small Sized Bowls and a Medium Sized Bowl and 10 Red and 10 Blue Balls.

Procedure:

- a. (i) Put 10 red balls and 2 blue balls in a bowl.
(ii) Ask the students what is the probability of drawing a red ball.
- b. (i) Put 4 red and 3 blue balls in the medium sized bowl.
(ii) Put 3 red and 3 blue balls in each of the small sized bowls.

(iii) Ask the students to put balls from the small bowls into the medium one to make the probability of drawing a red ball from the medium sized bowl $\frac{3}{5}$.

5. To Organize Learning of Concepts of Statistics-

Aim: To enable students to understand the concept of median.

Level of Class: Secondary

Material Required: Even and odd number of easily portable objects of different sizes (more than 3 in one group).

Procedure:

- a. (i) Take odd number of objects and ask students to arrange them in ascending/descending order of their size.
(ii) Ask the students to select the middle most item.
(iii) Repeat this activity a number of times.
- b. (i) Take even number of objects and ask students to arrange them in ascending/descending order of their size.
(ii) Ask the students to select the middle most item.
(iii) Guide the students to select the two middle most item and then calculate the average of their size.
(iv) Repeat this activity a number of times.

These are some few examples to guide teachers how to recognize learning of mathematics. Many more activities can be conducted inside or outside the classroom to relate Mathematics to the life and make it more meaningful, interesting, concrete and understandable.

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